

Deceptive Invitations in Academia: Navigating the Pitfalls of Predatory Publishing

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After a few days of publishing a new research paper in online journal, I received an e-mail that my article was found exceptional (?) and that they wanted my article to be published in their journal. I doubt the words being used by the editor-in-chief. No reputed, indexed journal approaches the author for publishing the article in their journal. It was the rarest rare for me.

The Mail was from - prof.isaac.cox.1945 [REDACTED]. Writing - 'After carefully examining the research articles you have published online, we were truly impressed by the exceptional quality of your work. It is with great pleasure that we extend an invitation to you to share any new research discoveries with our esteemed journal, SYLWAN. Founded in Poland in 1820, SYLWAN has established a strong reputation as a reputable peer-reviewed publication recognised for its excellence and significant impact within the academic community.'

I googled, checked on SCOPUS, and searched on Wikipedia. It seems correct. Then, I started reading their website carefully. - sylwan.ibles.org. There is no mention of the format they require on their web, and no specific citation style was preferred. And surprisingly, their review timing was seven days! I submitted a form

to asked details about the format and citation; the query reply time was twenty-four hours. More interesting was, if we want to read their past issue, they demanded to pay 650 USD. I was right; it was a fake journal. I also checked that a few more websites exist with similar domain names, including Sylwan in their web address.

The modes operands of such predatory journals are -

1. How do they contact you? If we publish a paper in online journals, metasearch, crossref or similar crawlers index its citation, including the author's name and e-mail. Such e-mail campaigners mine these data.
2. They dump and export this information as 'recently published papers' data.
3. They mail you by asserting that they either like your contribution to the field or that your paper is more qualitative and can fit into their journal.
4. In Mail, they use a prestigious journal name, Journals, which are indexed in databases such as SCOPUS, and Web of Science and have a year of legacy of

- publication. Journals, especially origin of Western countries.
5. They don't ask for or mention the publication fee initially in the Mail or on the website. Mostly.
 6. Their website interface provokes doubt, but sometimes it is hard as they pretend very well.
 7. They ask for Submission primarily by e-mail. I even observed that some such journals accept papers through WhatsApp. In many scenarios, their website has a form for submitting the papers.
 8. Read their turnaround time - they take seven days to a month for review. Most journals with track records take six months to even one and a half years to get published, and you get informed about every stage of the process through their submission system or via Mail.
 9. Predatory journals aren't even conscious of checking your document format, citations, spelling and grammar.
 10. Read their past issue. You can get plenty of understanding of what standards of papers and writing they seek or just put it for publication.
 11. Must check – Journal publication frequency. As it is a fraudulent business model, they are eager to publish articles as much as possible in a shorter time and at a higher frequency. In the above case, it was a monthly journal.
 12. After seven days of review, chances are high that they will accept the paper and ask for a publication fee, which is sometimes negotiable, too. Don't get attracted if you get some discounts.
 13. About South Asian journals, especially Indian journals, Apart from the above, one of their techniques is providing you with a discount if you become a peer reviewer. Or if you refer some authors with referral codes, inform them through the Mail.
 14. Such journals also publish articles in current issues, so don't be surprised if you see the changing index of such journals.
 15. Such journals have some common words asserting (In most case) on their title page: international, peer-reviewed, impact factor, as per UGC guidelines, bilingual, multilingual, etc.
 16. In the case of hardcopy, their publisher would be mostly a printing press or individual publisher. In the case of online, the probability of fake or sub-standard journals is high as you do not even know whom you are dealing with.
 17. As mentioned earlier, they accept papers and their publication charges through WhatsApp. Even if you use Mail, it will be an individual mail address, not an academic or professional domain Mail address.
 18. These journals (not necessarily fake, but low-quality or money-making journals) aren't dedicated to a single academic domain; they

all accept papers on science, humanities, language, social science, etc., in a single and same issue.

The lists of such observations can be long and more elaborate. I recommend researching the journals in which we are seeking to publish our articles. It is not about what we write but how our work can reach readers. It's not wrong to publish articles in non-indexed, unreputed, online or printing journals, but fakery and fraud in the name of genuine promises.

You may find many articles regarding fake publishers and scams in the academic and internet communities.

I am sharing my experience - during my PhD, where publishing papers was one of the tough challenges. The requirement of the UGC CARE listed publication is no longer required. Previously, receiving a UGC Norms certificate was essential while leaving the institution after your PhD. I wasted months finding such

indexed journals and paid thousands of rupees in the name of publication charges. I highly recommend you not to follow such national-level indexing, peer review, and impact factor journals unless it is getting published by a Good Institute and public university. Even if your research medium is other than English, please try to publish at least one article in an English journal in any international (other than your country) journal. You may need help translating your work into English. This counts in academic records and the recruitment process. Prioritise your paper to get published in internationally indexed journals such as SCOPUS, Web of Science, MLA Bibliography, etc., in your academic area and one co-authored publication with your supervisor. And have a publication frequency post-degree or research. Try contributing your work through journals, articles, or conferences at least once a year.

While typing this, I received another e-mail asking me to check out their journal for publication.